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IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES IN MEDICAL LABORATORIES

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EFLM will lead the laboratory medicine community for the shift to carbon neutrality in line with the European Green Deal (EGD) Investment Plan, also known as the Sustainable Europe Investment Plan, which is aimed at making Europe the world's first climate-neutral continent. Becoming the world's first climate-neutral bloc is a great challenge but also a great opportunity. It will be a challenge for clinical laboratories to achieve sustainable operations. Clinical laboratories use more energy and water than offices and generate huge amounts of hazardous and non-hazardous wastes every year. Due to their relatively high energy requirements, hospitals and laboratories must strive to achieve the long-term CO₂-reduction targets set by the European Commission. As the large consumers of energy, laboratories contribute to the largest percentage of carbon emissions. Incorporating sustainable practices into daily lab routine will go towards saving energy, reducing emissions, and helping the European Green Deal (EGD) to reach its Climate and Sustainability Action Plan. Laboratory medicine should contribute to a sustainable healthcare system ensuring that resources are used efficiently from ecological, social, and economical perspectives, while providing high-quality services to patients and physicians. Clinical laboratories can limit their environmental impact and provide sustainable laboratory services making reductions in four key areas – energy consumption, water consumption, waste production, and use of hazardous

chemicals. Establishing sustainable development goals and applying multiple means for reductions in these key areas, clinical laboratories can reduce their environmental impact. By being mindful of the environmental impact of everyday actions in a lab, and by taking steps to minimize energy, water, and hazardous chemical use, as well as waste generation, a clinical lab can be transformed into a safe, sustainable space. Sustainability measures should be a key feature in the rapidly changing healthcare environment to reduce their negative impacts on the environment and economy. Laboratory medicine community should lead the shift to carbon neutrality by decreasing their deleterious environmental impact and implementing efficient approaches to address the effects of climate change and pollution without compromising the quality of healthcare. In order to provide high-quality, effective, and safe healthcare services, sustainable healthcare systems need to overcome major economic and social challenges. Though there will be initial capital costs, there is a long-term cost-saving potential of a more efficient use of energy and other resources in healthcare systems: Despite this, there is a long way to go for environment-friendly hospitals, healthcare structures, and clinical laboratories to become the norm. Good collaboration among the EU healthcare systems and a common vision for future actions would help to achieve such goals.